

ISic0103

I.Sicily inscription 0103

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aio) · Virio · C(ai) · f(ilio) · Cla(udia)

2. Maximo · haruspic(i)

3. Clodiae · M(arci) · l(ibertae) · Donatae · m(erentibus)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Mommsen suggests as an alternative expansion of the last 'M' instead of .

Translation (en)

To the well-deserving ones, the haruspex Gaius Virius Maximus, son of Gaius, from the Claudia tribe, (and) Clodia Donata, freedwoman of Marcus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285287

EDR 127508

EDCS 22100056

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7355 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650797>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 21

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